

Information science communication, health, metrological media

ethics and peace

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Abstract

Although the data and results of the Phase III clinical trial of clopidogrel were found to violate logic, the invisible hand has become an obstacle to the official publication of the correct results of empirical research over the past decade, and justice, morality, market and regulation have also failed. Therapeutic guidelines resulting from incorrect results cannot be corrected. Many doctors doubt whether there is genuine medical ethics, evidence-based medicine, and morality in the mainstream media. Some media lack a sense of justice and conscience and often release false information to mislead the public. Similar phenomena are particularly prominent after the COVID-19 outbreak. Some disputes, conflicts and wars are usually caused or amplified by lies in the media. In this way, the Third World War is likely to break out as the media continue to create lies and escalate conflicts, and the sustainable development of the planet is hindered. Therefore, we suggest that new disciplines such as metrological media ethics, etc. should be established to conduct ethical evaluation or hierarchical management of media behaviors from a new perspective. An eight-level grading standard for media based on the publication of false information or rumors should also be established, so as to reduce the ability of inferior media to mislead the public, improve the public's ethical level, promote science communication of information, cultivate more champions of peace, build brotherly relations among nations, reduce the number of military and nuclear weapons, put an end to the development and use of genetic, biological, chemical and depleted uranium weapons, lower the number or intensity of wars or conflicts, and construct world stability, peace and sustainable development.

Keywords: clopidogrel · clinical trial · invisible hand · justice · morality · conscience · compassion · health · pharmacobehavioral economics · medical behavioral economics · post-truth · fake news · rumors · metrological media ethics · media ethics · evidence-based medicine · war · conflict · peace · peace fighter · champions of peace · world peace · depleted uranium · Gulf War Illness · Balkan syndrome · depleted uranium bomb syndrome · epidemiology · malignant hematological disease · tumorgenetic mutations · respiratory syndrome · neonatal malformations · premature aging · cataract

1. Introduction

We live in an era of continuous progress in science and technology. The establishment of a new discipline usually leads to a breakthrough in the development of this field. For the first time, the authors creatively proposed the establishment of a new medical or pharmaceutical or health discipline, such as pharmacobehavioral economics or medical behavioral economics or health behavioral economics, which will bring new opportunities for the development of related fields^{1,2}.

However, from 2012 to November 2022, this article was rejected by many English journals, mainly because they were not interested in it, rather than because the views or demonstrations in this article were wrong. Even if an article is rejected many times by the journal, it may be normal for any author. Conversely, we were surprised that the evidence-based medicine (EBM) data for the super blockbuster clopidogrel with global sales of more than \$90 billion are completely wrong and cannot be corrected¹⁻³, and that treatment guidelines or specialists consensus or medication habits related to the erroneous results of the Phase III CAPRIE trial of clopidogrel can't be corrected⁴⁻⁶. The treatment guidelines or consensus of specialists formed after the CAPRIE trial are based on false data and will excessively consume too much global medical resources¹⁻³. We are also surprised that some reputable journals, which place extreme emphasis on EBM results, turn a blind eye to errors or illogic in CAPRIE trial data. We are even more surprised that the safety of patients is not better protected. When our article is even refused to be published by a preprint platform on the grounds that the research content of this article is not within its scope (but in fact it is), we feel that the media has been

invisibly controlled by the hands of visible and invisible power and interests, and how insignificant individuals with justice are. Where is the scientific communication channel of relevant information of EBM? Some well-known doctors or professors who know this matter begin to doubt whether there is genuine medical ethics and real evidence-based medicine in Western medicine. Numerous doctors and professors have also begun to question whether there is real compassion, empathy, morality, and ethics in Western medical circles or mainstream media. We have to admit that despite the continuous development of science and technology, we are now living more in a “post-truth” era or post-morality or post-ethics era⁷⁻¹¹.

2. Taoist thought and justice, morality, empathy, editing or media ethics

Taoism has a long-term historical foundation in Chinese society. Taoism health preservation requires people to pay attention to the cultivation of their ideological and moral traits, which is regarded as the most important prerequisite for health preservation and longevity. Sun Simao, a well-known Taoist medical scientist, once taught health-keepers in China's earliest clinical encyclopedia *Qian Jin Yao Fang*, this way (roughly)¹²: Without virtue and moral values, people can't live long even if they have the elixir of immortality. Blessed are those who cultivate morality constantly even though they do not pray or seek longevity. Therefore, the cultivation of morality is the essence and key to health preservation. According to statistics from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), among the classics of various countries in the world, the *Tao-Te-Ching* is the handed down classic that has been translated into most languages and has the largest circulation¹³. Prigogin, the founder of dissipative structure theory and Nobel laureate, pointed out: "the description of nature by dissipative structure theory is very close to the traditional Taoist view of self-organization and harmony in nature¹⁴." Japanese physicist Nobel laureate Yukawa Xiushu pointed out in 1968: "Lao Tzu foresaw and criticized the prophet of human civilization defects more than 2000 years ago. Lao Tzu seems to see through the ultimate destiny of individual and whole human beings with amazing insight¹⁴. The German philosopher Nietzsche once commented that *Tao Te Ching*, a famous Taoist masterpiece, is like an inexhaustible well, full of treasure which is very easy to obtain¹⁴.

American scientist Will Durant, the winner of the Pulitzer Prize and Medal of Freedom, wrote in *The Story of Civilization*: “Perhaps we shall burn every book but one behind us, and find a summary of wisdom in the *Tao-Te-Ching*. It is indeed one of the most fascinating books in the history of ideas.” The former Chancellor of Germany Schroeder once appealed on television to every German family to buy a copy of *Tao-Te-Ching* to help solve people's confusion on ideas^{14,15}. Obama is one of the people who like to read the *Tao-Te-Ching*, and has repeatedly indicated that he can be elected president of the United States, and the great help comes from the *Tao-Te-Ching*¹⁶. On August 4, 2015, on Obama's 54th birthday, Ban Ki-Moon, former Secretary General of the United Nations, presented his Chinese calligraphy work "The best of men is like water" (English meaning) to the then president of the United States as a birthday gift. "The best good is like water" comes from *Tao-Te-Ching*, which refers to the highest level of good deeds of human beings, just like the character of water, it can help all things without fighting for fame and fortune^{16,17}. F. A. Hayek, the founder of spontaneous order theory and Nobel Laureate in economics, once said: "Therefore the sage says: I do nothing and the people are reformed of themselves. I love quietude and the people are righteous of themselves." in the *Tao-Te-Ching*^{14,17}, which is the classic expression of his spontaneous order theory. The great mathematician, philosopher Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz once praised "*Tao-Te-Ching*": This is the highest mystery of the universe¹⁴. The outstanding German scholar Ulysses Gerr once said, "maybe no one really understood Lao Tzu at that time, or maybe the time of really knowing Lao Tzu has not come yet¹⁴."

As the Chinese people have long been influenced by Taoism, they subconsciously advocate observing morality and upholding justice. Therefore, it is sometimes difficult to imagine that so many English journals will ignore morality and justice in the face of the illogic Phase III CAPRIE trial of clopidogrel and non-evidence-based medicine (Non-EBM), and occasionally we feel extremely miserable because of the lack of compassion in this society. In particular, while countless English-language media around the world advocate the importance of human rights and freedom almost every day, the human rights and interests of numerous patients with cardiovascular and

cerebrovascular diseases who have been taking clopidogrel are gravely damaged and their freedom severely restricted. Isn't it like there is a collective split in the thinking of global society? However, there are countless historical stories of how Allied forces led by the United States, Britain, and Russia etc. changed the course of World War II and maintained fairness and justice in the international community.

In the painful submission process, although we understand the difficulty of journal editors or editorial departments or the difficulty of survival, and articles that contradict the original positive results may bring trouble to the editorial department, we believe that in the future if evidence-based medicine is still needed as guidance for clinical medication, the effectiveness and safety of long-term clinical medication for patients should still be considered, the whole society or industry should not only attach importance to editorial ethics or re-examine editorial ethics or media ethics , etc¹⁸⁻²⁸. More consideration should also be given to developing and publishing a global declaration on editorial ethics or media ethics in Laozi's hometown to address various challenges.

3. Metrological media ethics, etc. and grading standard of media

We can often see that some media have no sense of justice and conscience in publishing information that they know is false^{7-9,26-28}. Some disputes, wars and conflicts are usually derived from the expansion of media lies.^{7-9,29-34} These false spam messages consume the public's time and may suppress the public's emotions. However, in real life, some people like or prefer to believe the false information released by some media and spread it frequently to mislead others^{7-9,17,26-28}.

Similar phenomena are particularly prominent in the prevention and control of COVID-19³²⁻⁴². Of the three classical elements of modern medicine to prevent infectious diseases, cutting transmission routes and protecting vulnerable populations are two extremely critical aspects. Otherwise, why do infectious disease doctors wear masks more often than others? In addition, masks were widely recognized in the early 20th century for preventing and controlling deadly infectious diseases. In December 1910, the plague broke out in northeastern China and spread rapidly throughout the three northeastern provinces⁴³. More than 1% of the total population died as a result of

the pandemic, especially in Harbin, which has almost become an "empty city". Wu Lien-Teh, the first Chinese to receive a doctorate in medicine from Cambridge University in England, was appointed by the government in 1911 to lead the fight against the plague. In the fight against the plague, Dr. Wu invented the first medical mask in Chinese medical history⁴³, which could filter respiratory droplets with yersinia pestis, thus preventing the spread of the plague and protecting the epidemic prevention personnel and the common people in the battle against the plague. Eventually, under Dr. Wu's direction, the deadly infectious plague that ravaged Europe in the Middle Ages was eradicated in just 67 days, saving millions of lives. This may be a major victory over the plague due to the shift in human behavior in infectious disease prevention and control 100 years ago, when medical behavioral economics was born as a separate discipline^{1,2}, and it also saved the economies of three provinces in Northeast China. Still, in 1,348, the world's second largest plague epidemic spread across Europe and Asia, killing an estimated 62 million people over a period of about 400 years. George Ernest Morison, a famous chief correspondent and statesman of The Times based in Beijing, wrote to Dr. Wu on July 9, 1911, and said: "Because of your achievements in controlling the recent plague epidemic, your name has become a household word in Europe and especially in Britain⁴³."

From the point of view of the dissemination of scientific knowledge, it should be entirely predictable that SARS-CoV-2 can be transmitted through respiratory droplets and can be prevented by masks. Surprisingly, 109 years after Dr. Wu's success or successful medical or health or hygiene behaviors in eradicating the plague, there are still some media, politicians or the public claiming that wearing masks is useless to prevent COVID-19³²⁻³⁶, which completely overturns the cognition of many ordinary people. These media outlets do not seem to be led or operated by people with normal scientific education, but the result of such disinformation is that it seriously interferes with the prevention and control of COVID-19, bringing chaos, consuming more public resources, and causing more people to become infected and die.

People want credible, impartial, objective and balanced news coverage in the wake of the pandemic, according to a report released on June 23, 2021 by the Reuters Institute

for Journalism⁴⁴. As the COVID-19 crisis has brought more demand for public health information, public trust in media coverage in Western Europe has increased. In the United States, on the other hand, distrust of the news is in the majority after a series of divisive political events. Based on the above problems and considerations, we believe that if we want to deal with the issues or challenges in the field of editing or media, perhaps the establishment of a more sophisticated discipline will be more likely to attract the attention of the whole society and more conducive to conducting research on or promoting the development of such fields, rather than just from the perspective of quantitative medical or pharmaceutical ethics (metrological medical ethics, metrological pharmaceutical ethics).^{1A,2A} In view of the fact that "the Tao Te Ching coincides with modern elements such as free politics, free legal system, market economy, science and technology, and the ideas and wisdom of the Tao Te Ching are loved and accepted by different leaders, philosophers, scientists and the public, the author believes that metrological media ethics or metrological journalism ethics (or quantitative media ethics or quantitative news ethics) should be established according to the characteristics of media work so that the public can use empirical analysis to measure or evaluate whether the editorial ethics or media ethics of a journal or media accord with moral norms, justice and conscience,^{2A,3A} and consider the deviation degree of justice and fairness. We believe that it is very important to carry out dynamic research on the media that like to published daily, weekly, monthly and quarterly, assess the degree of harm, and establish a ranking table of eight levels of standards for rumor media, which is of great importance for the classification and identification of lie media (Table 1), especially in the "post-truth era" or post-morality or post-ethics era,⁷⁻¹¹ which helps to improve the general public's ability to identify lies or the media that tell lies.

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Table 1. Grading Standard of Media Based on Publishing or Disseminating False Information or Rumors★

	General criteria for grading
1	The following are classified as Level 1 Liar Media or Mosquito Level Liar Media: (1) Which has published or disseminated 2 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 4 times within a week; or (2) which has published or disseminated 3 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 5 times within a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar

	<p>conditions; or (3) a journalist or media practitioner or media knowingly induces a third party to speak or provide certain information that is false or a rumor, so that its own media will not have to bear legal liability when reporting the information, and then they repeatedly hyped and reported the information twice within a week; or report this information 3 times cumulatively within a month; or 4 times accumulatively within 12 months.</p>
2	<p>The following are classified as Level 2 or Flies Level Liar Media: (1) That has published or disseminated 3 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 5 times in a week; or (2) That has published or disseminated 4 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 6 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and removal of the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or month or 12 months is 3, 4 and 5 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.</p>
3	<p>The following are Level 3 or Bedbug Level Liar Media: (1) Who has published or disseminated 2 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 3 times in a day, and 4 or 6 times in a week; or (2) 5 or 7 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and removal of the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or month or 12 months is 4, 5 and 6 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.</p>
4	<p>The following are Level 4 or Rat Level Liar Media: (1) That has published or disseminated 3 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 4 times in a day, and 5 or 7 times in a week; or (2) 6 or 8 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in</p>

	a week or month or 12 months is 5, 6 and 7, respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
5	The following are Level 5 or Fox Level Liar Media: (1) That has published or disseminated 4 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 6 times in a day, and 6 or 8 times in a week; or (2) 7 or 9 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and removal of the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or month or 12 months is 6, 7 and 8, respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
6	The following are Level 6 or Crocodile Level Liar Media: (1) Who has published or disseminated 5 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 6 times a day, and 7 or 9 times in a week; or (2) 8 or 10 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) The number of times of repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumor in a week or month or 12 months is 7, 8 and 9, respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
7	The following are Level 7 or Hippo Level Liar Media: (1) That has published or disseminated 6 pieces of fake news or the same piece of news 7 times a day, and 8 or 10 times in a week; or (2) 9 or 11 times in a month, after the above problems are found, they do not announce the correction and delete the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions, or (3) The number of times repeatedly hyping and reporting false news or rumors in a week or a month or 12 months is 8, 9 and 10 respectively, and the rest is the same as the third article in the Level 1 Liar Media.
8	The following are Level 8 or Dinosaur Level Liar Media: (1) which has published or disseminated 7 pieces or more fake news or the same piece of news 8 times or more in a day, and 9 or 11 times or more in a week; or (2) 10 or 11 times or more

<p>in a month, after the above problems are found, does not announce the correction and removal of the relevant false information or rumors at the same time under similar conditions; or (3) a journalist or media practitioner or media knowingly induces a third party to speak or provide certain information that is false or rumor, so that its own media will not have to bear legal liability when reporting the news, and then they repeatedly hyped and reported the news 9 times or more within a week; or report this news 10 times or more accumulatively within a month; or 11 times or more accumulatively within 12 months.</p>

★Note: A good friend in the United States is a Republican supporter and hopes that Trump will be re-elected as president. But the friend was very distressed that the US media lied, created scandals and covered up the truth every day during the presidential election, which led to the failure of President Trump's re-election. He thinks this media is lying practically 24*7 a week, and almost every piece of news is doctored fake news instead of a real report, so he is very angry. I feel a little sad for him because of his good friend relationship. I asked him how many pieces of false information a media release a day is acceptable to him? He said none of them were acceptable, and the news should be true and should not add personal comments. The author is not enthusiastic about politics, rarely reads American news, and cannot judge the authenticity of what he says. But seeing that a good friend is so disgusted with fake news, the author thinks that news ratings or media ratings should be necessary. Therefore, when the author feels his pain, it also triggers and reinforces the author's idea of grading false media. As a good friend of his, if he supports the Republican Party in America, the author may like the Republican Party more, and vice versa.

★Note: This classification standard is usually only suitable for a region or a country, and should be carefully judged by people in that region or country. When it goes beyond the scope, it is as if the author cannot judge whether the news broadcast by the media during the presidential election campaign or his presidency is false or real. When the author consulted friends on the classification of fake media, he thought that the classification standard of fake media should be determined according to the

influence of fake news. However, the author believes that the standard for judging the seriousness of false information may be a bit flexible and difficult to distinguish, so it is not included this time, and this standard can be further revised. Although the author did not set the grading according to the strict standards of American good friends, I hope that the loose grading model will be valuable to many people, and let him feel fair and impartial as a supporter of any party in the next election.

4. Discussion

4.1. False evidence-based medical data, false information, crises, wars, and methodologies for maintaining peace

EBM-based treatment guidelines can similarly be said to represent some kind of medical fairness or justice. Clinicians prescribe clopidogrel to patients according to the treatment guidelines or specialists' consensus or previous medication habits, and the manufacturers and managing enterprises benefit from them. In today's medical world, however, it seems very easy to formulate treatment guidelines or consensus for drugs. When data from the Phase III CAPRIE trial of clopidogrel became public, treatment guidelines for clopidogrel were quickly published. On the contrary, after the CAPRIE trial data was discovered to be illogical, our article was refused to be published publicly for more than 9 years, and the relevant therapy guidelines have been unable to be revised. Although the summary of this article was released at a 2013 medical conference, it is also searchable globally.¹

To our surprise and distress, the non-EBM problems in the CAPRIE trial were somewhat esoteric and difficult to understand, and the influence of top journals was greater than our proof of correctness. Some professors or physicians in the field of cardiovascular or pharmacology, or even epidemiologists with advanced degrees, still believe that the CAPRIE trial results are correct after reading this article, or are unable to determine whether the CAPRIE trial results are correct or not. Although some doctors trusted the results of articles published in top journals without thinking, some professors in cardiovascular, neuroscience, pharmacy or epidemiology were able to understand this article and confirmed that the core data and results of the CAPRIE trial were completely incorrect and illogical. The resulting treatment guidelines have resulted in

a huge waste of public health resources around the world. On such a key issue that is even difficult for medical or pharmaceutical experts to grasp, in accordance with the principles of morality and justice, relevant journals or media should stand up and promptly promote the analysis and judgment of EBM evidence and maintain its impartiality. However, such a situation has not yet occurred. The valuable information of medical science has not been scientifically disseminated.

Of the three classic elements described in textbooks on infectious diseases, cutting transmission routes and protecting vulnerable populations are the two most critical. Wearing a face mask is a common, simple and effective preventive measure for infectious disease physicians. In the early 20th century, masks were widely and effectively used to prevent and control deadly infectious disease pests. Conversely, in coronavirus prevention in the 21st century, although the number of people with higher education in Western society is significantly higher than in the early 20th century, they are repeatedly questioned or denied by the media and politicians as useless means. This has caused countless people around the world to lose their lives or leave the sequelae because they could not be physically isolated and infected with the novel coronavirus in time.

During the pandemic, false information, like the free mosquitoes in mountain areas in the summer of the COVID-19 epidemic, spreads everywhere, misleading the public, causing confusion, endangering epidemic prevention and control, interfering with economic recovery, without any effective restriction, but seriously affecting the control of the epidemic, consuming more public resources or causing more deaths, and becoming an important factor in triggering currency over trillion US dollars and causing a global economic crisis. The United States has nearly 100 million COVID-19 infections and more than 1 million deaths. The number of people with long-COVID-19 is enormous. Many of these disasters can be attributed to the contribution of inferior media.

Going back in time, some media lack a basic sense of justice when publishing information they know to be false. Some media outlets are happy to release false information. We can also observe that some disputes, wars and conflicts are often

caused and expanded by media lies, and media lies have even become a despicable means for interest groups to undermine peace and gain huge profits by relying on war behavior economy. It is also one of the important factors leading to the huge increase in the number of refugees in the world. Although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for a hundred years, it has failed to significantly change the situation where lying media and unscrupulous politicians create and promote conflicts and wars. Looking further, simply establishing the Nobel Peace Prize and praising several typical figures cannot solve the fundamental problem that global peace cannot be achieved. This means that major breakthroughs are needed in the methodology for achieving global security governance or maintaining global peace.

Taoist health preservation requires people to pay attention to cultivating ideological and moral qualities, and self-cultivation is the essence and key to health preservation. Among the classics of various countries in the world, the Tao Te Ching is the most widely translated and widely distributed. Scientists, philosophers, thinkers and politicians in Europe and the United States were impressed by the great ideas displayed in the Tao Te Ching. Former German Chancellor Schroeder even called on every German family to buy a Tao Te Ching book to help solve people's confusion about ideas. Therefore, according to the characteristics of media work, absorbing Taoist ideas, establishing an evaluation thought system with ethics and morality as the core and establishing a discipline of metrological media ethics will help combine modern scientific thinking with the precious thought essence of ancient philosophers, build a new theoretical system, purify people's thoughts, improve the quality of the global public, increase the number of peace loving leaders, and play its unique effect. It can be expected that this will play an exemplary role in reducing disputes, conflicts, wars, building harmonious societies and maintaining world peace.

The constant production of lies by the media will inevitably lead many people to go astray, lead to the waste or loss of many resources, and may destroy many lives and endanger the sustainable development of human society. Obviously, Through quantitative research on the behavior, quantity and degree of harm of false information released by the media, from the perspective of measuring media ethics, the media that

like to release lies or false information are evaluated and graded, and eight different evaluation standards and identification systems from mosquito level, fly level, bedbug level, rat level, fox level to crocodile level, hippo level and dinosaur level are established, as well as the ranking table of rumor media, It assists the media in ethical measurement and classified management.

. This would allow the public to fully understand or assess the level of media favouring lying or rumor-mongering; reduce the influence of lying or rumor media, and make excellent media stand out. It is believed that this will considerably enhance the global public's awareness of moral culture and moral level, and promote the scientific dissemination of information, which should be very conducive to public safety, social stability and sustainable development.

We believe that if the international peace organization can vigorously promote the application of metrological media ethics and the classification of lie media in the world, and classify rumor mongers from the perspective of morality and ethics, it will make most of the public recognize lie media rather than blind obedience after being hoodwinked, despise these media from the bottom of their hearts and fight against these media. This will undoubtedly help train more champion of peace ⁴⁵, reduce the number or intensity of wars or conflicts, promote world peace, promote people living and working in peace, and reduce the number of refugees worldwide. Metrological media ethics and the establishment of rankings to identify media that publish false information or lies may be one of the most powerful weapons we can use to build brotherly relations among nations, reduce the number of military and nuclear weapons, put an end to the development and use of genetic biological and chemical weapons, and change the world with ongoing regional crises, conflicts and wars.

The public should also be clearly aware that in a battlefield where there is no gunpowder, some financial fraudsters are using the media to carry out disinformation campaigns and continue to cheat the public of their wealth through virtual currencies or financial derivatives. Their revenues even exceeded those of the arms dealers who instigated the war, which seriously affected social stability and sustainable development.

If these disciplines and grading systems are organically incorporated into the annual

world peace conferences, it is believed that they will contribute to achieving quantitative or sustainable results in the promotion of world peace in public opinion and will complement the success of more world peace conferences. Even if the planet has to go through a third world war jointly launched by political, economic, financial, military and media lunatics in the future, the issues described in this paper should receive extra attention in order to control the peacekeeping situation afterwards.

4.2. Inspired by Nobel's Hope to Own a Newspaper

Ten days after signing his final will⁴⁵, Nobel also asked one of his nephews if it was possible to buy the free Stockholm newspaper Aftonbladet. Nobel hoped to own a newspaper, and according to himself, "it was inspired by free thought to oppose the remnants of force and other medieval eras." In my groundbreaking article on the establishment of a new discipline in measuring media ethics and the construction of a new theoretical system for promoting world peace, which disseminates justice and exposes evil, it has not only been published in some top English and ethical journals, but has even been refused official publication by international peace journals, the reasons they gave were basically disinterested. After this, the author deeply felt the foresight and sagacity of Mr Nobel. Freedom of speech cannot be enjoyed when the media are not controlled by impartial organizations.

The construction of media rankings has great daily operability, pushing the hierarchical management of the media to a new position, which can put media that falsify information and launch wars and disrupt peace in a difficult situation. If staff engaged in media ranking management establish daily or weekly updates of lie media rankings for countries or regions, it can be imagined that once such lie media rankings are released, they will inevitably form a great shock among the public in some regions or countries, and the media accustomed to spreading rumors will gradually lose traffic, market, and sense of existence. Some journals and media have shown resistance to the hierarchical management theory of practical media, which should be largely a reflection of their fear of publishing false information for quantitative analysis. This also confirms that the new theoretical construction of the combination of new disciplines and practices to promote the development of the world peace movement mentioned in this

paper should be taken seriously. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out hierarchical management of media and evaluate related media by using econometric media ethics.

4.3. The Explosion of Depleted Uranium Bombs in Ukraine by the UK Causes Serious Environmental Pollution and Enlightenment from the Collective Silence of the Western Mainstream Media

According to local media reports in Ukraine, on May 13, 2023, the ammunition depot in Khmelnytskyi Oblast was precisely hit and destroyed by Russian missiles^{46,47}, resulting in a violent explosion of a large number of depleted uranium bombs supplied by the UK to Ukraine, with a force equivalent to a magnitude 3.4 earthquake. Subsequently, a large number of toxic and radioactive particles created in the explosion floated into the air and continued to spread in the wind direction, drifting into the surrounding area. The Dnister River in Zhytomyr is experiencing an ecological disaster. Local journalists who conducted on-the-spot surveys of the local ecology after the ammunition depot explosion found that large numbers of fish carcasses had begun to appear in the river, large areas of aquatic life were dying, and beavers were beginning to die off one by one.

The reporter interviewed local residents⁴⁶, who said that after the explosion, the Ukrainian authorities were not sending anyone. There were no government or military personnel to inspect the damage caused by the explosion, and no one came to investigate the site. So they believed that there were dirty depleted uranium bombs supplied by Britain, stored in munitions depots, and that even the Ukrainian government was afraid to come. They themselves feared exposure to nuclear radiation, so nearby residents began spontaneously evacuating one by one. At the same time, these residents claimed that white foam had begun to float on the nearby river water source, so the ammunition depot was storing not only depleted uranium bombs but other types of chemical weapons. Now, to stabilize people's hearts, Ukraine and Poland have falsely claimed that it was just an "abandoned factory", while Poland has falsely claimed that nuclear pollution has not yet been caused. Romanian senators have claimed that a radioactive cloud covered 400km two days after the explosion of a depleted uranium bomb depot in Ukraine⁴⁸.

According to meteorological observation data⁴⁹, Ukraine is currently experiencing a westerly wind, which means that the air with depleted uranium bomb radiation dust is following the monsoon towards western Ukraine, in the direction of countries such as Poland. Further west of Poland are Germany, the Czech Republic, and France.

The depleted uranium bomb is one of the eight weapons banned by the United Nations. Some media said it was unacceptable that mainstream Western media had banned coverage even though five days had passed since the explosion of the depleted uranium bomb^{50,51}. It seems that Western countries have little knowledge of the explosion of Ukrainian ammunition depots. It is expected that the incidence rate of the following diseases will increase significantly in Ukraine, Poland and some European countries in the future: pulmonary nodules, thyroid nodules, fatigue, joint pain, gastrointestinal diseases, abortion of pregnant women, fertility decline, chromosomal aberration and genetic mutation in sperm and eggs, neonatal malformations, growth and development disorders, shortened life span, premature aging or early death, cataracts of the eye, respiratory syndrome, Gulf War Illness (GWI), Balkan syndrome, malignant hematology, testicular cancer, and other tumours. To make matters worse, Ukraine, an important food-producing site and a major global food exporter, has a large amount of black land. Once the land here is contaminated with depleted uranium bombs, it will exacerbate the world's food crisis.

When mainstream media are invisibly controlled by institutions with the same values, will freedom, democracy, morality, and civilization still exist? Will the truth still exist? Will Europe ever be healthy again? Do these people who dropped the depleted uranium bomb still have a conscience? If they thought it was a normal bomb, could these politicians, manufacturers and bombers have lived in Ukraine's Khmelnytskyi Oblast for a year? Their hearts may be made of rusty steel. Europe may have been turned into a barren desert by British politicians and depleted uranium bombs. It is impossible not to marvel at Nobel's vision and insightful approach to free media reporting and the purchase of a Swedish media company a hundred years ago⁴⁵.

After the explosion of a stockpile of depleted uranium bombs in Ukraine, when it was necessary for mainstream media to continuously report the truth and find solutions

to the problem, most of these mainstream media remained silent. Does this also remind us that we need to use metrological media ethics to assess which media are really used to maintain world peace? Because dealing with difficult issues can reveal a person's character, conscience, and ability, as well as the character, conscience, and willingness of a media outlet to maintain peace. In complex situations, for the sustainable development of the Earth and for a better world peace, should we consider rapidly changing the methodology and philosophy of maintaining world peace, which is still inefficient for a long time?

The half-life of depleted uranium is longer than that of uranium, reaching 4.5 billion years⁵², and can cause long-term damage to the environment and the human food chain. In view of the continuous shelling after the Zaporozhe nuclear power plant was occupied by Russia, and the crisis of serious damage to the nuclear reactor, even with the intervention of the United Nations, and Russia and Ukraine blame each other for their actions⁵³. European countries and international organizations seem to need to take prompt action to prevent the recurrence of shell attacks on depleted uranium stockpiles in the region, in order to prevent the further spread of nuclear pollution clouds to other European countries due to seasonal winds, resulting in more severe environmental pollution in Europe, permanent damage to water resources in some European countries, disasters for agricultural production and exports, and serious damage to public health. If left unchecked, it could lead to a crisis of survival for the European public.

If the Alps are also contaminated by radiation, Europe's high-quality tourism resources will be permanently destroyed, and the mineral water produced in the Alps exported to Asia will inevitably be abandoned by many users. This poses a real and long-term threat to Europe's economic recovery and sustainable development, and Europe's tourism economy will be affected to varying degrees.

Some epidemiological studies have confirmed the presence of Gulf War Illness (GWI) among 250,000 Gulf War veterans⁵⁴. Some people believe neurotoxins are the most likely explanation based on the various symptoms of GWI⁵⁵. The author and some friends believe that these explanations lack basic pharmaceutical logic. In a desert climate, sarin poison gas quickly breaks down into non-toxic products. A jar of sarin

poison gas with the lid open cannot fail to decompose quickly, and the toxicity cannot last for a month. If it is a sarin gas disease, the U.S. military that was exposed to sarin gas at that time should immediately have a large number of personnel showing symptoms of poisoning. Moreover, the U.S. military has never discovered weapons of mass destruction or chemical weapons, including sarin gas, in Iraq.

In order to unify the understanding of the hazards of depleted uranium bombs and avoid liability for their use, some friends suggest naming those who suffer from refractory respiratory syndrome, GWI, or Balkan syndrome due to working or living in depleted uranium bomb areas as “Depleted uranium bomb syndrome”. Before the disease is officially named, anyone who believes that the naming evidence is insufficient or opposes it should personally experience life for three months at any location in the center of a depleted uranium bomb explosion in Iraq, Serbia, or Ukraine to prove that they are not against peace. For those lacking funding, it is recommended to seek funding from the United Nations or the World Health Organization.

Moreover, the United Nations and the Security Council should not be two silent international organizations, but should show the necessary leadership and mobilize the United Kingdom to destroy all stockpiled depleted uranium bombs and raw materials, in order to prevent any uncontrolled actions by the UK from turning it into another nuclear radiation center brought about by war, leading to a surge in refugees fleeing Europe and unmanned areas in some parts of Europe. The United States is the world's largest military and economic power, and many members of the global public can almost hear various voices of the United States dominating the world from the news every day. The United States should take on the responsibility of leading and initiating peace operations, preventing the further expansion of the Russia Ukraine war, mobilizing Britain to destroy all depleted uranium bombs, so as not to make the global public think that the United States is like an arms dealer constantly searching for battlefields to sell weapons, and is indifferent to peace that quickly reduces civilian casualties.

4.4. The Most Ridiculous and humorous rumor making by Taiwanese Media (Composed of highly educated individuals)

In 2011, in order to create a long-term armed confrontation and non-peace with Chinese mainland, the Democratic Progressive Party of Chinese mainland even spread rumors to the people of Taiwan. People in mainland China were very poor and could not afford to eat tea eggs, instant noodles or meat, so they had to eat voles to supplement protein. However, over the past three decades, the price of tea eggs in mainland China has been ¥1~1.5 CNY(US\$ 0.14~0.21) per tea egg in almost every city. Today, 10 tea eggs in Wuhan cost less than ¥10 CNY (US\$1.4), and many tea eggs are sold every day. China is the world's largest producer and consumer of instant noodles. The price of instant noodles is very low. How can the public not afford instant noodles?

Taiwan's Democratic Progressive Party-controlled media said Ma Yingjeou, Taiwan's former leader, did not have a backseat on the high-speed railway during exchanges and investigations on the mainland between March and April this year. Dr. Wang Yichuan, executive member of the Taiwan Democratic Progressive Party and former director of the Taichung Municipal Transportation Bureau, stressed that the back seat on the high-speed railway was temporarily prepared for Ma Yingjeou while attending the political commentary program of the pro-green media Sanli News Station. A PhD from the Department of Transportation at a Taiwanese university made such absurd remarks in the era of self-media, which can easily be found in short news videos. However, some Taiwanese people still believe it to be true. It can be seen that once the media is controlled by people who have lost their conscience, spreading rumors is the norm. If the public is not slightly rational, they become fools or deceived.

Fig.1 Former Taiwan leader Ma Ying jeou took the high-speed rail from Wuhan to Changsha⁶⁰

^{1A} The definition of metrological medical ethics or quantitative medical ethics: a discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistical methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of medicine.

^{2A} The definition of metrological pharmaceutical ethics or metrological pharmacial ethics or quantitative pharmaceutical ethics: a discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistical methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of pharmacy..

^{3A} Metrological media ethics: A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistical methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the media field.

^{4A} Metrological journalism ethics: A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistical methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in journalism and communication.

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